

THEORETICAL AND LEGAL BASIS OF MATERIAL TECHNICAL SUPPORT

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An important condition for the dynamic development of the Republic Uzbekistan is an accelerated introduction of modern innovative technologies in the economic, social and other spheres with a wide application of science and technology achievements.

Rapidly developing all spheres of public and state life of the country require close support of ongoing reforms based on modern innovative ideas, developments and technologies that ensure a rapid and qualitative leap of the country into the ranks of the leaders of world civilization. In the conditions of independence, the Parliament of the Republic adopted two fundamental laws "On Education" [1]. The first law was adopted in 1992. The year 1997 dictated the need to revise the main directions of development of the education

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the problems faced by the military education system in the modern world, in an attempt to update and introduce innovative technologies that facilitate and improve the very quality of education. We reveal the root causes of the inhibition of the improvement process, show the importance and timeliness of updates and innovations, not only in the presentation of knowledge itself, but also in technologies that help to assimilate and master the acquired knowledge. We propose methods for a gentler introduction of innovations and show the importance of new influences into the modern system of military education.

system in the Republic. The law "On Education" and the "National Training Program" justified the basic principles of state policy in the field of education, defined the system and types of education in the Republic [2].

The Law "On Education" and the "National Training Program" have created the necessary legal framework for the progressive development of the educational system as a unified educational, scientific and industrial complex based on state educational institutions. The fundamental difference between educational reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the guarantees of the state in conditions for the gradual progressive development of the system of continuing education, state regulation of

the market of educational services and the proper quality of education.

An analysis of the existing education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan and a well-founded National model of personnel training shows that among the most significant shortcomings of the previously existing system of personnel training should be attributed to its inconsistency with the requirements of democratic and market transformations taking place in the country. There was a lack of close interaction and mutual integration of the education, science and production systems. Material and technical and information base of the educational process was insufficient, its observed lack of high-quality educational, methodological and scientific literature and didactic materials. The problem of ensuring a close relationship between the structure, content of education and the educational process, as well as the problem of organizing a system of continuing education, has not been solved.

By 2030, Uzbekistan will be among the 50 leading countries in the world according to the rating of the Global Innovation Index [5]. According to analysts, in order to achieve this noble goal, our compatriots should first of all strive to accumulate intellectual capital, and to allocate subsequent places to material and household needs. The 21st century is usually called the information age. Given the current way of life of mankind, it should be called rather an innovative century. Therefore, each country strives to strengthen the foundation of its development based on innovation. And Uzbekistan pays constant attention to this issue. Of course, innovation requires not only the development of modern

knowledge, but also the creation of innovations based on it. It was not for nothing that at the meeting held on December 18, 2018, dedicated to ensuring the need for President Shavkat Mirziyoyev paid special attention to this issue, as in the current era of rapid reforms, our country needs personnel that correspond to this pace. In fact, targeted actions in this aspect in our country began a year ago. By the decree of the Head of State dated November 29, 2017, the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established.

Consistent measures are being taken for the rapid innovative development of all sectors of the economy and social sphere on the basis of advanced foreign experience, modern achievements of world science, innovative ideas, developments and technologies. Projects that serve innovative progress primarily arise as an idea among young people and scientists with high scientific potential and deep thinking. The transformation of an idea into a final project and its implementation require support. In this regard, the Fund for Support of Innovative Development and innovative ideas. This foundation has organized a scientific internship for 21 young scientists abroad [4].

The introduction of the latest technologies into the education system refers to the introduction of a modern knowledge transfer system in the field of theory and practice. The development and the very course of education of modern youth occupies one of the main places in the science of our time, focused on the communication of knowledge, the development of the necessary skills in the practical part, the ability to think and soberly assess situations, on the formation

of the integrity of the personality of students. New implementations and changes in the process learning is dictated by the passage of time, the changed attitude to the process of learning, development and upbringing.

The introduction of new technologies in the education process makes it possible to keep up with the times, directing it in the right direction. From time immemorial, people have been afraid of everything unknown, new, it seemed frightening to them and they did not seek to follow new changes. The established stereotypes that exist in people's minds and relate to the usual way of life are very difficult to shake. People negatively affect the slightest changes in their comfort zone, thus, blocking innovations in the field of modern education and preventing the renewal of all types and forms of education.

Many are not ready to start studying theory from scratch, then passing exams, and most importantly, to change their established and outdated, in some areas, consciousness. And not an unimportant role in unwillingness is played by the fact that you will have to spend not only your personal time, but also your finances. But once the learning process starts, it is possible to stop it, thanks to specially developed techniques.

One of the most significant methods to check the effectiveness of the transformations implemented in the learning process is called:

1. The method of partial implementation, assumes under itself introduction of a separate newest, single element.
2. Another method - the method called "eternal experiment", involves an assessment and summing up of the results obtained over a long period of time.

3. Another method is the method of detailing documents. It is used to evaluate innovative introductions to the educational system, by crossing the possibility of extensive introduction of new technologies into the educational process.

The correct introduction implies a symbiosis of a new, modern and outdated educational process and investigation of the effectiveness of such an experience. Problems with the introduction of technological innovations, the education process is slowing down for several reasons:

1. A barrier to creativity. The teaching staff, working according to the old, rolled-up program, absolutely does not want to introduce innovations into their educational process. It is difficult for teachers to change their teaching style, there is a growing reluctance to develop, learn, improve themselves and change something. Therefore, all innovations in the education system are perceived by them with hostility.
2. Conformism, in another way — fitness and unwillingness to develop. It arises, perhaps, because of the fear of looking ridiculous and inappropriate in the eyes of other teachers. Because of this, teachers do not seek to adopt or find non-standard pedagogical solutions.
3. Personality anxiety, arises from lack of confidence in their abilities, in themselves, in their capabilities, low self-esteem. Because of this, teachers are afraid to express openly they have their own opinion and resist to the end any innovations in the education system.
4. Firmness of thinking. Many teachers of the old school suffer from this disease, who are sure that their opinion is the only true, correct, final and not subject to discussion.

Teachers don't try acquire new skills, experience, knowledge and react negatively to modern innovations in the educational process.

The latest behavior, based on innovative implementations, does not imply adaptability. It is focused on the formation of the personality of the individual, including self-development. The teacher needs to learn that the modern way of transferring knowledge is a method of educating a person in his harmonious integrity.

Rolled-up templates are absolutely not suitable for this, the main thing here is to think and make non-standard decisions, to look for a unique an approach and, moreover, to make your brain work in a completely uncharacteristic manner. The teacher is an officer who has successfully got rid of the narrowness of his thinking, various complexes, barriers in the psychological sense, can be a full-fledged participant in the introduction of innovations into the military educational system [3, p. 25-26.].

Innovative introductions into the education system of higher military educational

institutions, consists of several elements: the purpose of training, motivation in the transfer of knowledge and means to convey them, the content of the educational process. the process, participants in the educational process (teacher officer, cadets), the results of the educational process.

The technology involves two elements that are closely related to each other, since, to organize the activities of the cadet (student) and monitor the learning process. When identifying the results of learning technology, the main thing is to highlight the use of innovative, latest technological means, in another way - ICT. Traditional methods of education contain an overabundance of unnecessary information in academic disciplines. In the modern educational system, the educational process is organized in such a way that the teacher tries on the role of mentor. So, the main task of the innovation system is education is to teach the student to think broadly and analytically, to strive for self-development, to improve their skills.

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